

Faculty of Journalism in Al-Farabi Kazakh National University

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Abstract. The article introduces the faculty of Journalism in Al-Farabi Kazakh National University. It describes the benefits of studying in the faculty of journalism, some opinions of students and staff. The best qualities and advantages, studying habit, foreign exchange programs were also added.

Key words: Kazakh National University, Journalism, PR, students, education

Journalism is not an exact science, it is creative individual index. In mathematics, physics, chemistry, for example, at least a decade long laid down bases steadfast in this time interval. But journalism is required every minute self-identification and correction of their opinions. In other words, we are all affected by biased media. The faculty of journalism in Al-Farabi University is the oldest in the country. It employs well-known scholars and practitioners, recognized journalists in the country and abroad. The training process involves students from more than 15 countries and 50 professors from the world's leading journalism schools. Journalism students are working on the most modern equipment.

The primary task of the Faculty of Journalism is to train highly qualified journalists to work in local, national and international media organizations. Faculty of Journalism continues a long tradition of providing students with all the necessary knowledge and skills that will help them succeed in the profession of journalism.

The University is rich in talented students coming from different parts of Kazakhstan, as well as from abroad. Many of them are professional journalists and authors. Moreover, graduates of the Faculty of Journalism in leadership positions in many media companies in Kazakhstan. After completing his studies, each student will be able to find their place in the company's future leaders in the field of journalism.

The faculty consists of award-winning, recognized scholars who received their skills and knowledge in more than 20 countries, as well as journalists, writers, editors and operators.

Graduates of faculty work in almost all periodicals, television and radio, publishing houses and foreign bureaus, headed the editorial board of national and regional newspapers and magazines.

Specializations that the faculty offers:

- newspaper journalism, radio and television journalism,
- editing and publishing,
- International Journalism,
- advertising and public relations (PR)

At present, the quality of education confirms the high potential of the students knowledge on the subjects studied. The system of undergraduate and graduate programs as close to the leading educational systems in the world, making it easy convertibility of diplomas. Faculty scientists developed all regulatory, scientific and methodological basis for training. Today the faculty trains specialists who are highly demanded in the labor market.

At the University there are television and radio studios, print labs, where students produce a newspaper, but if you compare, for example, the University of Oklahoma, with whom we work, where students are doing the same thing, only this time on a professional level: the newspaper that they produce is of city level, radio and television, they broadcast in the city. Therefore, we need to rise to a higher level of quality. If there is stability, interaction with practical journalism, public organizations, these problems will be solved and the number of graduates will develop into quality".

International cooperation is one of the priority aspects of the activities of the faculty. Scientists of the Faculty of Journalism participate in seminars and conferences in the United States, Germany, Turkey, China and other countries. Close relationship is developed with Oklahoma State University, Columbia University, Duke University (USA), the University of Queensland (Australia), the Asia-Pacific Institute for Broadcasting (Malaysia), with the Faculty of Journalism of Moscow State University, Russian State Humanitarian University (Russia), etc. . From the period from 1995 to the present, more than 15 faculty members attended the University of Oklahoma, USA. They conducted a training exchange between teachers and students from foreign universities. About 500 graduates are annually marketed to media work and a large percentage of them are in the main journalistic "forge" of the country – journalism

faculty of Kazakh National University named after Al-Farabi. Every year it produces about 120 journalists in various fields.

Dinara Tumysh, a final year student of the Faculty of Journalism in Al-Farabi Kazakh National University:

"Last year I went to America to study at Huston Community College in specialization national journalist. I studied English literature and academic writing, sociology, how to write an essay, resume... approach to teaching and learning journalism. In order to enter the Faculty of Journalism preliminary six-month course must be passed. During the studies, you can chose the most suitable schedule for you. If you work, you can study in the evening, or vice versa, in the morning or build your learning process. Yes, and teachers are all working journalists, who while teaching get accustomed to the students, then to take to their work, conduct training.

The entire curriculum is balanced, 50% theory, 50% practice. There are taught how and what to write, how to work in practice, and not only the history of journalism. About two years are the main items, and other times – only in their specialty. In the US, different contests for the best essay, you can win a grant or discount. Students are friendly, despite being in different classes, together UNIVERSITY arrange picnics, and theater performances. After having joined the faculty of journalism, the applicant must be able to write well. After listening to a lecture on a particular subject, all the time we wrote the essay. And another important point: foreigners pay for their education and it is much more expensive than the Americans do, and, nevertheless, we have to tear up three skins. There are no exceptions and no refund. If you take less than 4 subjects you will be immediately deported”.

Tulegenov Genii, sports journalist, teacher of journalism in the faculty of Kazakh National University named after Al-Farabi:

"The level of education of current students is inferior to that which was in Soviet times. Then there was a lot of competition and the position of the teaching staff, and place in the media. Let's say, holding the diploma, you could go and know that you'll get a guaranteed spot if you get on the distribution in the province. Now the situation is such that due to the abundance of media students have the opportunity to practice immediately.

I think that the problems with getting a job at students now do not exist. But the main problem is that now there are complaints about the low level of work of the journalist. This is due to the fact that many of the students, after studying the first course or choose to work in the future specialization, believe that the theoretical knowledge

they are no longer needed, and therefore miss classes, get money and satisfaction from their work, not seeking to raise the bar of their journalistic skills.

All journalists are required, but the question is: what is it? I will say about my personal attitude: if a man comes and he has such qualities as honesty and desire to improve – I always take it to work, I will always help, always prompt.

That is, it all depends on the people themselves. Both from the teachers and from the students themselves. And when the students who study start to say, "I wish I did not study, I would spend more time working, – I fundamentally disagree. Because in his lectures and seminars keep saying: "We have a pulpit, there is head of the department, there are practical teacher, please come, pay for your education, you should take this knowledge".

I work in the newspaper "Pro Sport", I have seen and taught a lot of students. The practice, which they received from us, helped them find jobs in the future. That is, if you work with young people, they will grow mentally really fast. But not all journalists have the desire and ability to give their time and effort. Therefore, many students fall into this situation: they didn't succeed, they get refused, and get disappointed in journalism. But many executives of the same media holdings, news agencies do not have journalism education. Someone is talented from God, and someone can work as a good craftsman.

70% of graduates are traditionally passive in the process of development of knowledge, but work while studying, 25% of them are the future composition of the basic staff who carry the journalistic spirit, and 5% of the students become the elite that can go to the new stage of development, combining mastered, followed by self-developing potential.

In conclusion it is worth saying that Journalism is a flexible system, it is about new trends. In the Kazakh National University will come because it is the only oldest university of the country, and therefore can undoubtedly be called the best. Journalism in Kazakh National University named after Al-Farabi is the only university in the country, which produces adequate journalists. The faculty has long-way tradition.

Journalism creates guild form of consciousness in journalists. With all that students tend to rebel and demand more attention to themselves by teaching staff (faculty members), few people think about the number of links are accumulating in the walls of journalism penalty. However, in addition to the existing links with the 4 year undergraduate and two-year master's, there are stuff, through which you can go to the other threads and age group of journalists graduates of journalism. The very concept of the Faculty of Journalism in Kazakhstan has its own only penalty. Journalism School

is the largest in our country higher education institution, the first university on the status of the country. None of the university of Kazakhstan cannot say that its walls are trained more than 12,000 students.

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